

APPROACHES TO EXPANDING THE POSSIBILITIES OF COGNITIVE ACCEPTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article describes the scientific views and opinions of scientists such as pedagogues, psychologists, philosophers, philologists, and sociologists regarding the expansion of the possibilities of cognitive acceptance of professional knowledge by future teachers.

Key words and phrases: professional knowledge, cognitive acceptance, educational paradigm, cognitive technologies, historical-cultural, axiological, acmeological, functional, competence approach, tendency, principle, motivation.

БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРНИНГ КАСБИЙ БИЛИМЛАРНИ КОГНИТИВ ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИНИ КЕНГАЙТИРИШГА ОИД ЁНДАШУВЛАР

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада бўлажак ўқитувчиларнинг касбий билимларни когнитив қабул қилиш имкониятларини кенгайтиришда оид педагог, психолог, файласуф, филолог, социолог каби олимларнинг илмий қарашлари, фикр мулоҳазалари баён этилган.

Таянч сўз ва иборалар: касбий билим, когнитив қабул қилиш, таълим парадигмаси, когнитив технологиялар, тарихий-маданий, аксиологик, акмеологик, фаолиятли, компетенциявий ёндашув, тенденция, принцип, мотивация.

Changes in the field of education accelerate the transition to a new educational paradigm in the development of a future specialist. A number of approaches are being promoted in this area. For example, there is a strong need to rely on historical-cultural, axiological, acmeological, functional, competence approaches in preparing future teachers for such activities. In particular, the Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on February 7, 2017, "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", reflected on the possibilities of reforming the higher education system, considering the development of professional skills of young people. On the basis of this document, it is envisaged to carry out many scientific researches in the direction of improving the content of the higher pedagogical education system.

Raising the educational process to a new level of quality in general secondary schools, mastering international assessment mechanisms, organizing the educational process implemented in them based on innovative approaches is directly related to pedagogical activity. Decrees, decisions and laws adopted in our country create an opportunity to organize the processes of cognitive acquisition of professional knowledge of future teachers based on new approaches. This creates favorable conditions for improving higher pedagogical education based on new approaches, enriching the pedagogical processes implemented in them with new content and cognitive technologies. Therefore, developing a special program for the development of the higher pedagogical education system, solving the task of improving the management infrastructure of this system is gaining special importance, special attention is being paid to the development of scientific and methodological support.

As mentioned above, it is necessary to approach the quality of training of future teachers for professional activity in a new context.

Raising higher education to a new level of quality requires improving the content and mechanisms of teacher training based on new approaches. That is why improving the content and structural structure of the future teacher training system based on the requirements of the state and society is becoming the most urgent issue on the agenda.

The trends in the society of Uzbekistan show that the needs of students to learn are increasing day by day. Accordingly, new demands are placed on the level of knowledge and professional creativity of teachers working in the general secondary education system. This, in turn, requires future teachers to further develop the ability to master innovative mechanisms of activity in search of new knowledge.

Pedagogical theories aimed at developing the future teacher's cognition take into account the improvement of activities related to finding new knowledge, applying it in their practical activities, and turning them into professional competence. The cognitive ability of future pedagogues is manifested in the ability to use the mechanisms of ensuring students' independence, interest in the educational process, and the formation of their motivation to learn. For this purpose, it is necessary for future teachers to acquire the experience of helping children to be able to act clearly in changing situations, believing in their own strength. In addition, it is important that future teachers learn effective methods of working with parents.

The orientation of the process of higher pedagogical education to the student's personality implies the following. Taking into account the development trends of society, facilitating students to improve their educational activities and cognitively acquire professional knowledge is one of the important issues to be focused on. Only pedagogues with a high level of professional knowledge and independent work experience can effectively organize the educational process. Because in the process of education, students are required to have the opportunity to develop both personally and professionally. The educational process of a higher pedagogue should

be convenient for students to become a developing profession, successfully mastering professional knowledge and turning it into competencies.

The quality of higher pedagogical education is regularly improved based on the social order. Through this process, students are provided with pedagogical knowledge necessary for professional development.

The new content of higher education, based on the cognitive principle, is directed to the systematic development of students' professional competencies. For this, first of all, the content of higher pedagogical education should serve to ensure students' cognitive acquisition of professional knowledge. Our observations show that the process of cognitive assimilation of knowledge and the formation of competencies by future teachers is not scientifically and pedagogically supported. That is why it is envisaged to pay special attention to the development of the student's cognition in the training of future teachers. The activity of students' learning is of great importance in the formation of the professional competences of future pedagogues. In order to raise higher pedagogical education to a new qualitative level, it is required to increase the effectiveness of the use of didactic tools aimed at expanding the possibilities of cognitive assimilation of the knowledge of future teachers. Because today, the scope of innovative methods and technologies, principles and approaches to their improvement is expanding. It is required to use world experience in this field.

The new quality of higher pedagogical education is ensured not only by its content but also by the personality of a pedagogue working in a general secondary education institution. His attitude to acquiring information acquires special pedagogical importance in this system.

In order to acquire the apex of professional skills, future teachers must have the ability to cognitively master pedagogical knowledge.

One of the main points of attention in education is to ensure coherence and continuity between all its stages. Today, the scope of research aimed at improving the quality of education is expanding. Its basis is to determine to what extent the requirements for education in new conditions have been met and what results have

been achieved. The increase in the demand for improving the quality of higher pedagogical education requires the cognitive assimilation of knowledge and the identification of students' needs. The essence of the innovative approaches to determining the quality of education is primarily related to the expansion of opportunities for the cognitive acquisition of knowledge and turning it into the competencies of future teachers.

Experts have emphasized that professional competencies are integrative. Professional competences represent the ability of a person to effectively perform his or her activities in socio-pedagogical situations (R.Safarova, N.Muslimov, B.Khodjayev).

Competence (lat. *compe*to-I am achieving, I am worthy, I am worthy) represents the professional knowledge and experience of the pedagogue. The quality of higher education, as a didactic category, expresses the perceptions of the subjects of the educational process about the changed working conditions, the educational process, and its results, and allows one to determine the specific features of this system. Such an approach represents the professional abilities of future teachers and its basis is the activity of cognitive assimilation of knowledge. For example, the future teacher will receive quality education in the process of mastering the knowledge necessary for pedagogical activities; Cognitive mastery of pedagogical activity techniques by future teachers, as a result of which students will acquire competencies in independent thinking and the application of professional knowledge in practical activities in various educational situations. In the course of higher pedagogical education, there is an opportunity for professional training of students who have the ability to cognitively master professional knowledge. For this, it is appropriate to widely use cognitive technologies in the process of higher pedagogical education aimed at training future teachers. The process of higher pedagogical education organized based on the principles of democracy and humanism acquires a special pedagogical significance when it is implemented, taking into account not only the professional knowledge of students but also their inner world, inclinations, and

aspirations. In this process, the main task of pedagogues is to find and use the means, methods, and technologies to realize the personal potential of students and to ensure their spiritual and cultural development. For this purpose, it is assumed that future teachers will carefully master the tools and methods that help the personal development of students and the expansion of their knowledge. Because the idea of comprehensive support for a developing person has been put forward by many pedagogues and psychologists, for example, in the works of E. Goziyev, A. Davletshin, R. G. Safarova, I. P. Ivanov, Sh. A. Amonashvili, A. V. Mudrik, etc., special attention is paid to expanding the scope of professional activity of the pedagogue. In their work, they have a unique approach to organizing the process of mastering professional knowledge of future teachers.

The formation of competences for future teachers' cognitive assimilation of professional knowledge is carried out in a specially organized pedagogical process. Improving the system of training future teachers in the process of higher pedagogic education based on a cognitive approach implies the regular development of students' professional competencies.

Future teachers acquire the secrets of pedagogical skill (acme) through the cognitive acquisition of professional knowledge in the process of higher pedagogical education. Such knowledge includes the personal professional experiences, competencies, and cognitive abilities of the pedagogue. It is assumed that the future teachers will have knowledge and professional competences that will give them the experience of continuous development and support of students. All-around development and support of students is one of the main functions of the teacher, to ensure their intellectual development, mental and physical health, opportunities for mutual communication and cognitive success. The goal of using cognitive technologies in the process of higher pedagogical education is to prepare future teachers for complex professional activities. This, in turn, requires improving the system of training future teachers based on a cognitive approach.

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